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Design and Optimization of a Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine

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1. Abstract

The intent of this research project is to investigate the design and optimization of a horizontal axis wind turbine blade. The primary focus is to determine the optimal twist and chord distribution to maximize the blade's overall performance. Furthermore, linearization of these distributions is used for ease of fabrication considering the large theoretical scale of the blade. The blade in question is designed for a three-bladed 5 MW turbine with a tip speed ratio (λ) of 7 at a rated wind speed of 11.4 m/s and rated rotational speed of 11.5768 RPM. For the majority of the design process, blade element momentum theory (BEM) is employed using Matlab. To achieve this, the blade is discretely represented using 35 elements in order to determine localized blade loading and performance. Based on the results of BEM calculations, the optimized blade has an overall power coefficient (C_p) of 4.4938, while the linearized blade has a power coefficient of 4.4. In order to validate the results of the BEM calculations, the blade was modeled and tested using Qblade. Since both methods showed similar results, the calculations are deemed to be an accurate model of the blade's performance.

2. Introduction

In recent years, wind energy has become an increasingly viable source of renewable energy. This has resulted from the development of more advanced, efficient, and reliable designs. Countries such as Denmark have demonstrated how successful and cost-effective the integration of wind energy into existing grid infrastructure can be. In some cases, the cost of energy generation has decreased as much as 40% within the last 20 years (Krohn et al., 2009). Turbines such as the Dongfang Electric 26-megawatt (MW) offshore turbine, built in 2024, are capable of

a power output as large as 26 MW, which is a significant improvement over earlier designs such as Lammefjorden turbines, which only had a rated output of 2 MW. These design improvements have attracted much international attention, and wind energy had been adopted by 67 countries as of 2017 compared to only six countries in 2005 (Darwish et al., 2019). The potential growth of wind energy systems is vast and remains largely untapped. With continued development and investment, this technology has the greatest potential for reducing the reliance on non-renewable energy sources.

Wind turbines rely on lift generation along the length of the blade; pressure distribution creates rotor torque, which is used to generate power (Kahn et al., 2022). This allows wind turbines to harness kinetic energy in the wind and convert it to usable electric power. This study focuses on the horizontal axis class of wind turbines (HAWT), as they possess superior efficiency when compared to vertical axis wind turbine turbines (VAWT). Furthermore, HAWTs are easier to control than VAWTs as the blade's pitch, nacelle's yaw, and the rotor torque can be controlled.

Figure 1. Configurations of horizontal and vertical axis wind turbines. (Kahn et al., 2022)

Blade pitch is controlled to regulate the rotational speed of the rotor as the free stream wind speed approaches and exceeds the cut out wind speed by adjusting the blade's angle of attack to induce stall. Yaw controls allow the rotor nacelle assembly to rotate about the tower's axis to keep the rotor perpendicular to the direction of the oncoming wind. HAWTs are also equipped with a disc brake to further regulate the rotor's rotation in the case of high wind speeds. These control methods allow the turbine to operate at peak efficiency while preventing structural failure.

While there are many numerical methods used in the design of a wind turbine blade's complex geometry, blade element momentum theory (BEM) is a particularly common approach due to its computational simplicity and efficiency. This method discretizes the the blade into annular segments in order to evaluate the blade's aerodynamic performance at each spanwise position (Manwell et al., 2024). This method operates under the assumption that there is no aerodynamic interaction between elements, the forces on the blades are determined by 2-D aerodynamic coefficients, and that the relative wind at each radial position is known (Manwell et al., 2024). This method can be used to determine blade performance, twist and chord distribution, rotor torque, and rotor power output. While this method is very robust, it does have its limitations such as the inability to account for three-dimensional aerodynamics, interaction between radial elements, and unsteady flow conditions. Despite this, the BET method does provide a reasonably accurate model of the blade. Additionally, Qblade is used a complimentary method to validate the results of BET calculations obtained in Matlab. The results of these calculations yield an optimized blade geometry; however, this geometry is not ideal for the blade design at a large scale due to the large chord and twist angles near the root region of the blade.

This would complicate the fabrication of the blade as well as increase its overall cost.

Furthermore, the root region of the blade has the lowest contribution to the overall power generation of the blade due to the comparatively low relative wind velocity and torque. In order to simplify the root geometry of the blade, linearization is employed to optimize the chordal and twist distribution with minimal reductions in the power output of the blade.

3. Design process and methods

3.1 Determining initial design parameters

The overall design process began with defining the initial design parameters of the blade in order to determine necessary intermediate variables. The turbine is designed with 3 blades (B), a design tip speed ratio (λ) of 7, a hub diameter (D_{hub}) of 3 meters, a initial estimated power coefficient C_p of .45, a estimated drivetrain efficiency (η) of .9, and a rated power output of 5MW. These value are used to obtain the necessary radius of the blade required to generate the rated power.

$$P_{rated} = \eta C_p \frac{1}{2} \rho \pi (R_{blade}^2 - R_{hub}^2) U_{\infty}^3 \quad (1)$$

The blade's rotational speed it determined using the calculated radius.

$$RPM = \frac{60 U_{\infty} \lambda}{2 \pi R_{blade}} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega = RPM \frac{2 \pi}{60} \quad (3)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{U_{\infty}}$$

Table 1: Design parameters of wind turbine

Wind Turbine Rated Power (P_{rated})	5 MW
Wind turbine rated speed (U_{∞})	11.4 m/s
Tip speed ratio (λ)	7
Air Density (ρ)	1.225 kg/m ³
Estimated initial power coefficient (C_p)	0.45
Hub diameter (D_{hub})	3 m
Blade radius (R_{blade})	65.82 m
Drivetrain efficiency (η)	0.9
Number of Blades (B)	3
Rated rotational speed (ω)	11.5768
Airfoils	NREL S811 at root, NREL S813 at root and transition

Figure 2. Forces acting on annular section of wind turbine blade (S. Pradhan & S. Chitrakar, 2022)

3.2 Airfoil selection

The process of airfoil selection was defined by the need for an airfoil that possessed a high lift to drag ratio as well a suitable thickness to withstand aerodynamic and structural loading. To determine the aerodynamic characteristics of the selected airfoils, the airfoil needs to be evaluated over a range of angles of attack to determine the optimal angle of attack where the lift to drag ratio is highest.

Figure 3. NREL S811 (blue), NREL S812 (yellow), NREL S813 (blue) airfoil geometries, cylindrical airfoil (green)

The specific airfoils that are investigated are the NREL S811 and NREL S813. Qblade is used to determine the coefficient of lift (CL), coefficient of drag (CD), and the ratio of coefficient of lift to coefficient of drag with respect to angle of attack. These airfoils are ideal for the application in question as they are able to generate significant lift at low wind speeds due to their cambered design. This proves particularly beneficial for reducing the cut in wind speed of the turbine's rotor. Furthermore, the S811, S812, and the S813 were selected from a thick family of airfoil where the maximum thickness of the airfoils was 26.26%, 21%, and 15.99% of the airfoil's

chord, respectively. This ensures that the blade is able to withstand the immense structural loading at the theoretical scale. In order to simplify the design process, only the S813 and S811 airfoils were selected for the final design of the blade. Figure 4 illustrates the relationships between $CL-\alpha$, $CD-\alpha$, and $CL/CD-\alpha$ for the NREL S811, NREL S812, and NREL S813 airfoils.

Figure 4. Extrapolated airfoil data showing

airfoil performance at a range of angles of attack for the NREL S811 and S813 airfoils at $Re = 6000000$

The results of the extrapolated airfoil data illustrates that the ratio of CL/CD increased with the angle of attack until the effects of drag take over and the airfoil stalls. The data from Qblade is entered into Matlab in order to find the optimal angle of attack for each airfoil, that is, where the ratio of CL/CD is greatest. Based in the results of the data, the optimal angle of attack for the S811 and S813 airfoil is 5.5° and 6° respectively.

3.3 BEM design process for wind turbine blade

Blade element momentum theory (BEM), a combination of blade element theory (BET) and the momentum theory, is used to determine the forces and torque acting on turbine blade sections. This method allows for the forces as well as the torque acting on the blade, and thus the power produced by the blade, to be determined. The forces acting on the blade are illustrated in

Figure 2, lift force (dF_L), drag force (dF_D), tangential force (dF_t), normal force (dF_n), differential torque (dQ), and differential thrust (dT), the values of which are obtained for each blade element using the BEM method. For the analysis of the blade, the airfoils are defined for the root, midspan, and tip regions. For this blade design, the S811 airfoil is used from $r/R = .08$ to $r/R = .3$ and the S813 airfoil is used from $r/R = .3$ to $r/R = 1$. Note that for the section of the blade ranging from $r/R = 0$ to $r/R = .08$, a cylindrical cross section is used. However, this is not relevant to the BEM calculations, as the cylindrical cross section does not have a significant aerodynamic contribution. For each airfoil, the aerodynamic coefficients occur at the optimum angle of attack, that is, the angle of attack corresponding to the maximum value of CL/CD . In order to evaluate the blade using the BEM method, it must be discretely represented using segments, occurring between non-dimensional radial positions. The number of segments dictates the resolution of the blade model. For the purposes of this project, 35 segments are used, resulting in a high resolution model of the blade. Using this discretized blade span, the blade's local tip speed ratio (λ_r) is obtained using the following equation.

$$\lambda_r = \lambda \left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \quad (4)$$

The local tip speed ratio can then be used to find the angle of relative wind (ϕ) for an ideal rotor.

$$\phi = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2}{3\lambda_r} \right) \quad (5)$$

The local blade solidity is given by equation 7.

$$\sigma = \frac{BC}{2\pi r} \quad (6)$$

Using these values, axial (a) and angular (a') induction factor can be found using equation 8 and 9.

$$a = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{4\sin^2(\phi)}{\sigma C_l \cos\phi}} \quad (7)$$

$$a' = \frac{1 - 3a}{4a - 1} \quad (8)$$

Tip losses for the blade are given by equation 12.

$$F_i = \frac{2}{\pi} \cos^{-1} \left[\exp \left(- \left(\frac{\frac{B}{2} \left(1 - \frac{r_i}{R} \right)}{\frac{r_i}{R} \sin(\phi_i)} \right) \right) \right] \quad (9)$$

Using equation 13, the overall power coefficient for the blade can be determined.

$$C_P = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{8\Delta\lambda_r}{\lambda^2} F_i \sin^2 \phi_i (\cos \phi_i - \lambda_{r_i} \sin \phi_i) (\sin \phi_i + \lambda_{r_i} \cos \phi_i) \left[1 - \left(\frac{C_d}{C_l} \right) \cot \phi_i \right] \lambda_{r_i}^2 \quad (10)$$

Note that $\Delta\lambda_r$ can be determined using the following equation:

$$\Delta\lambda_r = \lambda_{r_i} - \lambda_{r_{(i-1)}} \quad (11)$$

The relative wind velocity can be found using equation 15.

$$U_{rel} = \frac{U(1 - a)}{\sin(\phi)} \quad (12)$$

Using the previous calculations, the values for differential lift force (dF_L), drag force (dF_D), normal force (dF_n), tangential force (dF_t), thrust force (dT), rotor torque (dQ), and power (dP) can be calculated.

$$dF_L = C_l \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{rel}^2 c dr \quad (13)$$

$$dF_D = C_D \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{rel}^2 c dr \quad (14)$$

$$dF_n = dF_L \cos \phi + dF_D \sin \phi \quad (15)$$

$$dF_t = dF_L \sin \phi - dF_D \cos \phi \quad (16)$$

$$dT = B \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{rel}^2 (C_L \cos \phi + C_D \sin \phi) c dr \quad (17)$$

$$dQ = B \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{rel}^2 (C_L \sin \phi - C_D \cos \phi) c r dr \quad (18)$$

$$dP = \Omega dQ \quad (19)$$

Note that by calculating the sum of the differential power, the total power can be obtained.

3.4 Twist and chord distributions

Using the BEM method, the sectional chord can be determined using the chord and twist distribution for a Betz optimum blade. Equation 20 is used to determine the chord distribution which results in a chord length that is large at the root of the blade and tapers off towards the blade tip as seen in Figure 5. Note that the value for coefficient of lift is not constant, but dependent of the airfoil used in specific blade segment.

$$c = \frac{8\pi r \sin(\phi)}{3BC_L \lambda_r} \quad (20)$$

The section pitch (θ_p) and twist angle (θ_t) can be determined using equation 10 and 11 respectively. Note that the control pitch angle (θ_c) is equal to zero at the rated wind speed. The sectional twist is dependent on both the inflow angle and the angle of the attack. The optimum angle of attack used for the sectional airfoil is 5.5° and 6° for the S811 and S813 airfoil respectively.

$$\theta_p = \phi - \alpha \quad (21)$$

$$\theta_t = \theta_p - \theta_c$$

(11)

Figure 5. Chord and twist distribution for the wind turbine blade.

Using the results of these calculations, the optimal blade geometry (as shown in Figure 6) is obtained using Qblade.

Figure 6. Optimal blade model.

One of the considerations during the airfoil selection process was ensuring a smooth transition between the root region and midspan/tip region airfoils. While the S812 airfoil was initially considered, using it in the design interrupted the transition from the root region to the midspan region and the midspan region to the tip region as shown in figure 7. For these reasons, the design was simplified and only the S811 and S813 airfoils were used.

Figure 7. Chord and twist distribution for the wind turbine blade using the S812 airfoil from $r/R = 0.3$ to $r/R = 0.7$. After determining the geometry of the optimum blade, it is necessary to create a linearized design for ease of manufacturing and cost reduction. Linearizing the blade geometry is especially necessary for the root region of the blade where the twist angle and the chord are the highest, as this would present the greatest challenge to the fabrication of the blade. Furthermore, the root region of the blade produces significantly less torque relative to the tip region and thus has a lower overall contribution to the power produced by the blade. This renders it unnecessary to preserve the root region's geometry from the optimized blade. To linearize the blade and obtain a

good approximation of the optimized design, the following relations can be used where a_1 , b_1 , and a_2 are coefficients the linearized chord and twist distributions.

$$c_i = a_1(R - r_i) + b_1 \quad (22)$$

$$\theta_{T,i} = a_2(R - r_i) \quad (23)$$

These coefficients are altered as necessary to create an approximation of the optimal blade geometry that minimally alters the tips geometry, as seen in figure 5. Based on the optimal blade geometry, the best fit for the linearized design was obtained using the coefficients $a_1 = 0.05$, $b_1 = 2.5$, and $a_2 = 0.10$. This results in blade design shown in figure 8.

Figure 8. Final linearized blade design in CAD (left) and Qblade (right)

4. Blade simulator Qblade

4.1 Numerical simulations in Qblade

Qblade uses the BEM method to evaluate the aerodynamic performance of a wind turbine blade. It can also be used to determine the performance of onshore and offshore wind turbines in various wind conditions. For the purposes of this project, Qblade is used to support the BEM calculation in Matlab and validate the overall blade design. To create the blade in Qblade, it is

discretized into the same number of segments used for the BEM calculations in Matlab. The blade's geometric parameters (chord, twist, length) is then entered into Qblade to create a model of the blade. Blade performance is calculated using Qblade's BEM solver. Using this model, a turbine can be create to simulate the behavior of the blade at different wind speeds as shown in figure 9.

Figure 9. Wind turbine model in Qblade

The results of this simulation show that the power output of the turbine at its rated wind speed and tip speed ratio is 4.909 MW. Table 2 shows the parameters and results for the simulation and figure 11 shows the turbine's power curve.

Table 2: Qblade wind turbine simulation parameter

Wind Turbine Rated Power Output (P_{out})	4.909 MW
Wind speed (U_{∞})	10 m/s
Tip speed ratio (λ)	7
Air Density (ρ)	1.225 kg/m ³
Power coefficient (C_p)	0.54
Hub height	90 m
Blade radius (R_{blade})	65.82 m
Torque	4.82×10^6 Nm
Number of Blades (B)	3

Figure 10. Linearized turbine power curve

Furthermore, a structural simulation can be conducted to calculate maximum deflection of the blade under aerodynamic loading as shown in figure 11.

Figure 11. Structural analysis of design blade

This simulation shows the maximum out-of-plane bending the blade experiences is 5.65 m. The results of this simulation could be used to inform the aeroelastic design of the blade in order to minimize its deflection by altering the materials used and pre-bending the blade. Table 3 shows the simulation parameters for the structural model of the blade.

Table 3: Simulation parameters for structural model of the blade

Modulus of Elasticity for shell material (E)	2 e+10 Pa
Shear Modulus for shell material(G)	7.5 e+9 Pa
Density of shell material	1850 kg/m ³
Modulus of Elasticity for internal material (E)	2 e+11 Pa
Shear Modulus for internal material(G)	7.5 e+9 Pa
Density of shell material	7845 kg/m ³
Spar angle	0 degrees
Spar position (percent of chord length)	25%
Shell thickness percent	0.05%
Spar thickness percent	.2%
In plane tip deflection (y-axis)	-0.436 m
Out of Plane tip deflection (x-axis)	5.65 m

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Comparison of Qblade and Matlab results

In order to demonstrate that the results of the BEM method calculations obtained using Matlab are meaningful, they are compared to the results from Qblade. The simulation in Qblade is used to validate the predicted performance of the blade designed in Matlab. This ensures that the design is capable of meeting the target performance parameters and demonstrates that the design process was correctly executed. To achieve this, a theoretical model of the turbine was created in Qblade using the linearized blade geometry. The simulation is then conducted at an average wind speed of 10 m/s, which results in the turbine's theoretical power generation, torque, power coefficient, and rotational speed as shown in Table 2. In Matlab, a similar simulation is conducted at the same wind speed. The theoretical power generation is 4.91 MW and 4.909 MW in Matlab and Qblade respectively. This indicates that the turbine's power output is accurately modeled in both softwares. The power coefficient is 0.54 and 0.438 in Qblade and Matlab respectively. The value of the power coefficient given by the Qblade simulation is 22% greater than that derived from the Matlab calculations, and while it is still reasonable, it results in a power output of approximately 6 MW using the equation 1. This indicates that

there is potential error made in Qblade as the power coefficient is greater than it should be.

The values of the rotor torque are 4.0548×10^6 Nm and 4.82×10^6 Nm in Matlab and Qblade respectively. The result from Qblade is approximately 19% greater than the Matlab result. While this is notable discrepancy, the difference is still acceptable as the results are reasonably similar.

6. Conclusion

The objective of this project was to determine the blade geometry for a three-bladed 5 MW turbine with a tip speed ratio (λ) of 7 at a rated wind speed of 11.4 m/s and a rated rotational speed of 11.5768 RPM. The project primarily focused on determining optimal chord (c) and twist θ_t distribution to maximize its overall performance. The blade design was then simplified through linearization using the optimized blade geometry to guide this process. Using the BEM method in Matlab and Qblade, the blade's performance was evaluated and the design was validated. Overall, the results proved that the blade was capable of generating the rated power value at the rated wind speed. While there were some discrepancies between the two computational methods used, they both yielded reasonably similar results, indicating that the initial calculations using the BEM method were performed properly. The project successfully yielded a blade that met the design requirements while illustrating in detail the necessary design process.

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